

Access to and specifics of detailed national LFS data – the case of Slovenia

Sebastian Kočar
Social Science Data Archives
University of Ljubljana

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The content of the presentation

- How to access LFS microdata in Slovenia?
- What microdata are available to different types of users?
- EU-LFS and Slovenian LFS (ADS survey) differences
- Preparing LFS microdata
- Preparing metadata for LFS microdata
- Distribution of LFS microdata and metadata
- Promotion of LFS microdata use
- Plans for the future

Access to LFS microdata in Slovenia

- Microdata available to registered researchers/PhD students working with registered researchers
- SORS research data lab
- SORS remote access connection (large secure public administration network)
- Anonymised data (EU LFS equivalent protection) on CDs
- The process is fairly quick and simple, takes approximately 1-2 months (Data Protection Committee)
- PUF versions are available on ADP website for free (simple online registration, takes 1 day)

LFS microdata for different types of users

<i>Type of users/microdata</i>	Deindividualized LFS microdata	Anonymised LFS microdata (SUF)	Public Use LFS microdata (PUF)
Registered researchers	Research data lab/remote access	CDs	Available on ADP website (simple registration needed)
PhD students	Research data lab/remote access	CDs	
Students	No access	No access	
Public	No access	No access	

EU-LFS and Slovenian LFS (ADS survey) differences

- Variables (additional variables in SORS databases)
- The level of protection (EU anonymisation criteria)
 - Aggregation (e.g. 5-year bands)
 - Top- and low- coding
 - Numeric data -> Categorical data - Deciles (e.g. income)
- Time series distributed (SORS series starts in 1995)

Preparing deindividualized LFS microdata

- preparing deindividualized microdata in the safe room environment
- SPSS is used, SPSS syntax is written
- variable and value labels, missing values are added to the dataset; additional logical control is made, unneeded variables are deleted, variables in databases are connected to codebooks used
- by using SPSS syntax prepared, microdata can be exported in any desired format, readable by variety of software used by researchers

Preparing LFS Public Use Files – the purpose of it

- the majority of researchers would benefit from a simpler access to moderately anonymised microdata
- undergraduate students/potential researchers are not familiar with SORS microdata (can't access them in the detailed form), so they are not aware of the advantages of using them
- the anonymization procedure keeps as much statistical information intact as possible, data are of sufficient quality to be used for advanced level of research

Preparing LFS Public Use Files – how we do it

- in cooperation with SORS Sector for General Methodology and Standards (following very strict rules)
- anonymisation procedure which follows Eurostat LFS anonymisation criteria (in SPSS) + sampling in R! (using packages `sdcMicro`, `bethel`, `samplecube`) + recalculation of weights
 - + better quality of data
 - time consuming
- anonymisation using μ -ARGUS
 - + simple and fast
 - suppression of values

LFS METADATA – structured metadata for researchers

- DDI 2 standard is used
- study descriptions are being prepared, ADP DDI extended scheme is used – including methodological, file description, data description, publication, other material etc. metadata fields
- all the required/useful documentation is made available to researchers in one place (codebooks, questionnaires, publications, syntaxes, methodological explanations etc.)
- metadata is being harvested from SORS and EUROSTAT documentation and websites, also by contacting separate SORS departments, responsible for conducting a survey

Distribution of LFS microdata and metadata

- LFS metadata, including descriptive statistics for LFS variables and metadata documentation, are publically available (ADP website)
- HTML browsing document was prepared (for research data lab, remote access)
- PDF study descriptions (DDI standard) are available to all researchers (research data lab, remote access)
- Easy-to-use microdata are already stored on the research data lab hard disk (protected), could be easily transferred to researcher's folder

Promotion of LFS microdata use

- Microdata are under-used, research potential
- Mailing lists
- DwB project
- International conferences and workshops
- National workshops
 - For students
 - For researchers

Plans for the future

- Continuation of the work done (preparing LFS 2012 and 2013 microdata and metadata)
- Including ad-hoc modules
- LFS PUFs
- Selection of key standard socio-demographic concepts, writing routines
- Workshops for microdata users
- Preparing microdata and metadata for other surveys

Thank you for your attention!

Sebastian Kočar

sebastian.kocar@fdv.uni-lj.si

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

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